

**Spectrophotometric Studies of 3-(2-Furanyl)-
2-propenohydroxamic Acid Chelates**

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HYDROXAMIC acids have received considerable attention as analytical reagents for various kinds of metals¹. Formation constants of the transition metal chelates have also been evaluated by different techniques. Rowland and Meloan² investigated 2-furo- and cinnamohydroxamic acid chelates spectrophotometrically and reported the compositions and the molar extinction coefficients of various chelates. Brahma and Chakrabarthy³ reported the stabilities of cinnamohydroxamic acid chelates of La^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} in 3 : 1 dioxane-water medium by pH titration technique. So far, no spectrophotometric work has been done on the stabilities of 3-(2-furanyl)-2-propenohydroxamic acid chelates. The present communication deals with determination of stability of 3-(2-furanyl)-2-propenohydroxamic acid (FPHA)

(1) with vanadium(v) and uranium(vi) by spectrophotometric technique.

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vanadate and uranyl nitrate respectively, and standardised. The ligand was prepared following the reported procedure⁶. Buffer solutions (pH 2 and 7) were prepared using known procedures⁷.

Spectra were recorded on a UV-DEC 340 spectrophotometer. An ITL digital pH/MV meter with glass electrode (DPH-14) was used to record pH.

Experimental

Stock solutions of metal ions vanadium(v)⁴ and uranium(vi)⁵ were prepared from ammonium meta-

Results and Discussion

The composition of the complexes determined by Job's method of continuous variation, slope-ratio

TABLE 1—YATSIMIRSKII'S METHOD

[V]=[L]=0.0015 M, Final volume [V-FPHA]=30 ml ;

[U]=[L]=0.002 M, Final volume [U-FPHA]=25 ml

ϵ_{\max} [V-FPHA]=1.079 2 × 10⁴, ϵ_{\max} [U-FPHA]=9 344 × 10³ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹

Metal taken=3 ml, Temp.=30 ± 0.1°

System	Absorbance	Total ligand concn. Cl × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	Equilibrium ligand concn. [L] × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	Molar extinc. coeff. $\bar{\epsilon} = A/CM \times 10^{-3}$	$Y = 1/[L] \times 10^{-4}$	$f_1 = \bar{\epsilon}/[L] \times 10^{-7}$	$f_2 = (f_1 - a_1)/[L] \times 10^{-10}$	$g_1 = (\bar{\epsilon} - b_1)/[1/L]$
V-FPHA	0.517	2.4	1.442 0	3.446 7	0.693 5	2.390 2	—	-0.922 0
	0.529	2.5	1.519 6	3.526 7	0.658 1	2.320 8	—	-0.959 3
	0.575	2.9	1.834 4	3 833 3	0 545 1	2.089 7	-3.054 4	-1 102 0
	0.728	3.7	2 350 8	4 853 3	0.425 4	2 064 5	-2.490 6	-1 172 2
	0.829	4.3	2.763 6	5.526 7	0.362 0	1.999 8	-2 353 0	-1 191 5
	0.958	5.0	3.224 6	6 386 7	0.310 1	1.980 6	-2 075 4	—
U-FPHA	0.803	3.52	1.801 2	3.345 8	0.555 2	—	—	-1.378 6
	0.881	3.84	1.954 3	3 670*8	0.511 7	1.878 3	—	-1.432 3
	1.061	4.64	2.369 0	4.420 8	0.422 1	1.866 1	-1 662 7	-1 558 7
	1.250	5 60	2.924 5	5.208 3	0.341 9	1.780 9	-1.633 2	-1.694 0
	1.325	6.00	3.163 9	5.520 8	0.316 0	1.744 9	-1.628 0	-1.733 9
	1.402	6.40	3 399 1	5.841 6	0.294 2	1.718 6	-1.592 8	-1.753 3
	1.475	6.80	3.642 9	6.146 8	0.274 5	1.687 0	-1.572 9	-1.768 4
	1.538	7.20	3.908 0	6.408 3	0 256 0	1.639 8	-1.587 0	-1 793 6

TABLE 2—LUNDEN'S METHOD

[V]=[L]=0.0015 M, Final volume [V-FPHA]=30 ml ;

[U]=[L]=0.002 M, Final volume [U-FPHA]=25 ml

ϵ_{\max} [V-FPHA]=1.0792 × 10⁴ ; ϵ_{\max} [U-FPHA]=9.344 × 10³ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹

Metal taken=3 ml, Temp.=30 ± 0 1°

System	Absorbance	Total ligand concn. Cl × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	Equilibrium ligand concn. [L] × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	Equilibrium metal concn. [M] × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	Degree of complex formation $\phi = CM/[M]$	$\phi_1 = \frac{\phi - 1}{[L]} \times 10^{-3}$	$\phi_2 = \frac{\phi_1 - \beta_1}{[L]} \times 10^{-6}$
V-FPHA	0.517	2.4	1.442 0	1.021 0	1.469 1	3.253 1	5.500 0
	0.599	2.8	1.689 9	0.945 0	1.587 3	3.475 3	6 008 0
	0 693	3.2	1.934 2	0.867 1	1.729 9	3.773 6	—
	0.829	4.3	2.763 7	0.731 8	2.050 0	3.799 2	—
	0.887	4.5	2.856 2	0 678 1	2.212 0	4.243 4	6.244 0
	0.958	5.0	3.224 6	0 612 3	2.449 8	4.486 0	6.313 9
U-FPHA	0.803	3.52	1.801 2	1.540 6	1.557 8	3.096 8	—
	0.881	3.84	1.954 3	1.457 1	1 647 1	3 311 2	—
	1.061	4 64	2.369 0	1.264 5	1.898 0	3.790 6	—
	1.250	5 60	2.924 5	1.062 2	2.259 4	4.306 4	1.125 4
	1.325	6.00	3.163 9	0.981 9	2.444 2	4.564 6	1 121 9
	1.402	6.40	3 399 1	0.899 6	2 667 8	4.906 6	1.145 0
	1.475	6.80	3 642 9	0.821 4	2.921 8	5.275 4	1.169 5
	1.538	7.20	3.908 0	0.754 0	3.183 0	5.586 0	1.169 6

and mole-ratio methods in 30% ethanol-water medium indicates the metal-ligand ratio to be 1 : 2 for both the systems. Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out at 344 nm for red-orange vanadium(V) complex at pH 2, and at 348 nm for yellow coloured uranium(VI) complex at pH 7. The chelates follow Beer's law in the concentration range $0.2-1.2 \times 10^{-4} M$ V^V and $0.12-1.2 \times 10^{-4} M$ U^{VI} .

Determination of stability constants :

Yatsimirskii's method : According to Yatsimirskii's method, a series of subsidiary functions f_1 , f_2 , \bar{z} , and g_1 are constructed for both the systems from the absorption values by mole-ratio technique. The values calculated are reported in Table 1. The calculated values of f_1 and f_2 are plotted against free ligand concentration at equilibrium [L] and extrapolated to zero value of [L]. Exponential curve and linear regression analyses were employed to calculate the intercepts a_1 and a_2 . The functions \bar{z} and g_1 are plotted against [1/L] and extrapolated to zero [1/L]. The values of the intercepts b_1 and b_2 are also calculated using regression analyses. The calculated values for V-FPHA complex are $a_1 = 2.65 \times 10^7$, $b_1 = 9.84 \times 10^3$; $a_2 = -4.2 \times 10^{10}$ and $b_2 = -1.52$. The values of the intercepts obtained in a similar manner for U-FPHA complex are $a_1 = 2.26 \times 10^7$, $b_1 = 1.1 \times 10^4$; $a_2 = -1.84 \times 10^{10}$, $b_2 = -2.17$. From the intercept values, stability constants are calculated using the equations,

$$\beta_1 = \frac{a_1 b_1 - a_2 b_2}{a_1 b_2 + b_1^2} ; \beta_2 = \frac{a_1 - b_1 \beta_1}{b_2}$$

Leden's method : For both the systems, series of subsidiary functions ψ_1 and ψ_2 are calculated from the degree of complex formation (ϕ) and the values are reported in Table 2. The functions are plotted against equilibrium ligand concentration [L]. The overall stability constants can be directly obtained as the intercepts on the ordinates from these plots.

Table 3 reports the stability constants of the FPHA complexes of V^V and U^{VI} . It is seen that the values of $\log K_2$ are lower than those of $\log K_1$ for both the systems, except the Leden's method value for U-FPHA system. This is in accordance with that of the statistical factors.

TABLE 3—STEPWISE AND OVERALL STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR V^V AND U^{VI} CHELATES

Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$				
Method	System	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Yatsimirskii's	V-FPHA	3.54	3.17	6.71
Leden's	V-FPHA	3.39	3.32	6.71
Yatsimirskii's	U-FPHA	3.46	3.17	6.63
Leden's	U-FPHA	3.00	3.97	6.97

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